

Research Article

Further Evidence of an Association Between the Ratio of Substance P to 5-HIAA/Cr and Delayed Chemotherapy-induced Vomiting

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Abstract

Purpose Substantial evidence support the role of serotonin and substance P as mediators of chemotherapy-induced vomiting. Preliminary data suggested that the numerical ratio of the two neurotransmitters could be a novel marker associated with delayed emesis. However, because of the small number of subjects and variable treatment regimens in the early report, additional patients were enrolled into the clinical study to determine whether the association persisted in a more homogeneous group of subjects.

Methods Pre-chemotherapy blood and urine samples were obtained in patients, all of who received high-dose melphalan. Measured substance P (sP), 5-HIAA (the primary serotonin metabolite), and creatinine (Cr) values were used to calculate each subject's sP to 5-HIAA/Cr ratio; the ratios were then ranked, highest to lowest. For each ratio, the corresponding outcome of delayed emesis was monitored for 120 hours following initiation of chemotherapy. Between-group difference based on the presence (+) or absence (-) of moderate to severe vomiting was analyzed by Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test (Oneway ANOVA).

Results Of the 23 patients enrolled in the study, delayed vomiting occurred in 10 patients beginning approximately 72 hours after chemotherapy. Mean values of the ratio of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr, 90.59 and 16.71, in the (+) and (-) emesis groups, respectively, were significantly different.

Conclusion The results from this cohort of patients are in accord with our previous publication. Moreover, data consistency alone should not undermine the novelty of the current findings; the only component of this paper that was not original was the methodology and use of the previously identified ratio.

Introduction

Nausea and vomiting have traditionally been coupled as a chemotherapy-induced adverse effect, although prevention has been incrementally more successful for vomiting than nausea [1]. Inherent in this somewhat skewed success is the inference that the two symptoms are (or at least partially) separate physiological processes. Indeed, much of what is known biologically relates to the symptom of vomiting. Furthermore, of the two well-defined and temporally-distinct phases of chemotherapy-induced vomiting (CIV), relatively greater improvement has been achieved in the acute phase compared to the delayed phase [2,3]. This conclusion is strongly supported by results of numerous clinical trials which implicate serotonin and substance P (sP) as the primary, although not necessarily exclusive, mediators of the early and late phases, respectively [4-9].

Despite the progress made toward reducing the incidence and severity of these symptoms, the frequently espoused goal of preventing nausea and vomiting has not yet been fully achieved [10]. While this conclusion is applicable to patients treated with standard doses of anticancer therapies, symptom

control can be even more problematic in patients undergoing hematopoietic stem cell transplant (H-SCT). Notably, current antiemetic guidelines exclude drug and drug dosing in the SCT setting.

Autologous SCT remains the treatment of choice for transplant-eligible patients with multiple myeloma. While the emesis risk of standard oral dosages of melphalan is classified as minimal [11-13], clinical experience indicates that high-dose melphalan (HD-Mel) used as conditioning for autologous transplantation is associated with moderate, and sometimes severe, vomiting, especially in the delayed phase. Because of the variability in incidence of late symptom development and the uncertainty regarding pharmacokinetic (and pharmacodynamic) interference of melphalan, the NK₁ receptor antagonist, aprepitant, was not routinely used for emesis prophylaxis.

In a previous publication, we found an association between a relatively high pretreatment ratio of sP to 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid/creatinine (5-HIAA/Cr) and risk for delayed vomiting [14]. It should be noted that the number which correlated with the terms "relatively high ratio" maximized the separation between patients that developed or did not develop emesis. Hence, at that time, and because of the

preliminary nature of the research data, the selected between-group cutoff point was very arbitrary. In addition, even though the majority of the treatment regimens were classified as moderately emetogenic, the study involved a heterogeneous group of patients with different tumor types.

In this report, we extend on our early findings in an attempt to further refine our ability to identify patients, *a priori*, at risk for developing delayed emesis. However, in contrast to the preceding publication, the current data were obtained from a more uniform cohort of patients, all of who received a HD-Mel conditioning regimen prior to autologous stem cell transplantation. The aim of this paper is to provide further evidence of this novel marker and its association with delayed vomiting.

Patients and Methods

The clinical research study received full approval of the Institutional Review Board of West Virginia University. Complete details of the methods associated with this research study have been reported previously [5]. As such, only a brief recapitulation of the study methods is presented here.

Patient eligibility was based on the following criteria:

- 1 .diagnosis of multiple myeloma and candidate for hematopoietic stem cell transplantation,
- 2 .conditioning regimen restricted to single dose of melphalan that requires hematopoietic stem cell support (i.e., >125 mg/m²),
- 3 .performance status: 0 to 1 by Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group standards,
- 4 .absence of baseline nausea and vomiting, and
- 5 .signed informed consent form.

Study design

Patients who met the above criteria were eligible to participate in this clinical study. None of the patients received antibiotics or opiate analgesics; and mucositis, a sequelae of HD-Mel did not occur during the 5-day study observation period. As such, multiple confounding factors were identified and eliminated in order to focus on *chemotherapy*-associated vomiting primarily. At the time this study was being conducted, all patients received the standard antiemetic combination of a 5-HT₃ receptor antagonist (ondansetron, 24 mg by mouth) and dexamethasone, 20 mg intravenously, 60 minutes prior to chemotherapy; both agents (same doses) were repeated the following day. None of the patients in this report received prophylactic aprepitant. Blood and urine were collected in a single instance, within 2 hours prior to chemotherapy. Administration of chemotherapy began at approximately 1300 hours in all patients. Specific information related to number of emetic episodes and grading of nausea was obtained from all patients through daily contact and evaluation. Moderate to severe delayed vomiting (the primary endpoint) in this study was defined as >3 episodes occurring after the first 24 hours (up to 120 hours) following initiation of chemotherapy. Although delayed vomiting may begin earlier than this

arbitrarily determined time, 24 hours has been most frequently used to define the separation between acute and delayed symptoms.

Neurotransmitter measurement

Substance P

Approximately 3 mLs of peripheral blood was collected in serum separator tubes. In order to stabilize the protein, 500 KIU/mL of aprotinin was added to the blood samples within five minutes of collection. The blood was allowed to clot, then centrifuged at 1000 x G for 10 minutes at 4C. Serum was removed and diluted 1:2 with the kit assay buffer. Substance P was measured using a commercially available immunoassay (Substance P Assay, Parameter™, Catalog Number KGE007, R & D Systems, Inc. Minneapolis, MN). The assay is based on the competitive binding technique in which sP present in a sample competes with a fixed amount of horseradish peroxidase-labeled sP for sites on a mouse monoclonal antibody. In brief, during incubation the monoclonal antibody becomes bound to the goat anti-mouse antibody coated onto the microplate. Following a wash to remove excess conjugate and unbound sample, a substrate solution is added to the wells to determine the bound enzyme activity. The color development is stopped and the absorbance is read at 450 nm (uQuant™, Bio-Tek Instruments, Winooski, VT). The intensity of the color is inversely proportional to the concentration of SP in the sample. All samples were tested in duplicate as recommended by the manufacturer.

Serotonin

Because 5-hydroxyindole acetic acid (5-HIAA) is the major serotonin metabolite, the breakdown product was determined to be a reliable surrogate of the neurotransmitter. After adjusting the pH of the urine specimen with hydrochloric acid, the appointed metabolite and creatinine were quantitatively assayed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), Arup Laboratories, Salt Lake City, Utah, 84108.

Data analysis

Based on our previous findings, absolute values of sP and 5-HIAA/Cr were used to calculate the ratio of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr. This specific ratio was chosen because clinical trials assessing the efficacy of 5-HT₃ and NK₁ receptor antagonists suggested sP has a relatively greater role in the delayed phase compared to serotonin. sP to 5-HIAA/Cr ratios were arranged numerically, highest to lowest (Table 1); for each ratio, the corresponding outcome (i.e., development and timing of delayed vomiting) is also noted. Between-emesis group variance (log[mean]) for patients who did (+) or did not (-) develop moderate to severe delayed emesis was analyzed by Oneway ANOVA, JMP™, Version 10.0.1, SAS Institute, Cary, NC.

Results

Demographics of the entire cohort of patients are shown in Table 2. Of the 23 subjects enrolled in this study, 10 (4 males/6 females) developed moderate to severe delayed emesis frequently beginning

approximately 72 hours after chemotherapy; none of these 10 patients had vomiting symptoms in the acute phase. Among the 13 remaining patients who had no episodes of emesis, five complained of nausea. Mean values of the pretreatment variables for patients with (+) and without (-) emesis were 90.59 and 16.71, respectively. Non-parametric analysis of the ratio of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr indicated the between-emesis group variance was significantly different, $p=0.0239$. Because of the wide range of values, Table 1 also shows that a possible association exists between neurotransmitter ratios and delayed emesis. From this table, a selected cutoff ratio of >69 appears to distinguish subject likelihood of late symptom development.

Patient code	sP to 5-HIAA/Cr ratio	Delayed emesis	Melphalan dose (mg/m ²)
82	254.1	Y (began ~72 h)	190
69	137	Y (began ~72h)	175
65	125.2	Y (began ~72h)	200
77	103	Y (began >96h)	127
75	77	Y (began ~72h)	168
55	70	Y (began ~80h)	200
66	69.5	Y (began ~80 h)	180
76	69	Y (began ~96)	140
79	58.3	N	175
86	37.2	N	200
51	32.3	N (mild nausea)	200
74	31	N	140
71	21.2	N (moderate nausea)	175
56	11.8	N	200
80	10.8	N	140
72	6.2	N	200
54	3.9	N (severe nausea)	175
61	2.3	N	200
73	1.1	N	200
52	<1	Y (began ~60h)	200
59	<1	N (mild nausea)	140
63	<1	Y (began ~48h)	200
64	<1	N	200

Table 1 Ratios of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr ranked, highest to lowest, with corresponding outcomes of delayed emesis. Red line denotes maximal, though arbitrary, separation between subjects with and without the delayed symptom.

Age in years, mean (range), 59 (37-71)
Gender (number patients)
Male (12)
Female (11)
Performance status, ECOG, (number patients)
0 (21)
1 (2)
History of alcohol consumption (number patients)
None (21)
Rarely (2)
Occasionally (0)
Regularly (0)
History of motion sickness (number patients)
Yes (0)
No (23)

Table 2 Demographics of enrolled subjects.

Discussion

Although our understanding of the emetic syndrome has increased over the past 100 years, the precise neurochemical mechanisms of nausea and vomiting remain incomplete. Even the impressive results of clinical trials demonstrating the efficacy of pharmacologic antagonism of the 5-HT₃ and NK₁ receptors are tainted somewhat by the less than complete abrogation of delayed symptoms, especially. Nonetheless, the outcomes of numerous clinical studies strongly implicate serotonin and sP as the principal mediators of the early and late phases, respectively [4,5]. Given their well accepted roles, we sought to add further credence to our previous finding [14].

Analysis of data in patients who were treated with a single high-dose of melphalan again shows that the pretreatment ratio of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr appears to be associated with risk of developing *chemotherapy*-associated delayed vomiting. Of note, the correlation of this ratio was observed at the (nearly) identical cutoff point we observed previously. Using the current cutoff point (i.e., ≥ 69), the positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall predictive value (OPV) are 100%, 86.6%, and 91.3%, respectively. (The values found in our prior paper were 88.9%, 81.2%, and 84%, respectively) [14].

These data notwithstanding, their significance could be minimized by a number of salient issues. First, because these estimates (of predictive value) were obtained *post-hoc*, it is uncertain how accurate

they may be when used prospectively. Nonetheless, accumulating data with regard to circulating sP suggest that the measured levels are in a relatively well-defined range and may constitute a reasonable reference range. Moreover, and despite the wide range in baseline sP values, the majority (20 of 23) of patients had mean levels comparable to previously reported values both in healthy men and women as well as patients with cancer [5,15]. It should also be noted that much lower plasma sP levels were reported by another group who used a different assay kit [16]. Despite differences in assay methodology, the minimal degree of cross-reactivity to neurokinin B (1.1%), substance P₍₈₋₁₁₎ (1.4%), and substance P₍₁₋₇₎ (<0.1%) suggests a relatively high specificity to sP in our study. Second, in spite of the apparent association between the ratio of sP to 5-HIAA/Cr and risk of delayed CIV, the precise biochemical mechanisms for symptom development remain uncertain. However, concordance data of sP and its role in delayed emesis have been published [17]. Furthermore, while serotonin is widely accepted to be the major mediator of the acute phase of the emetic syndrome, it is also reasonable to suggest that serotonin could contribute to the delayed vomiting process. This is consistent with the finding of beneficial effects of 5-HT₃ receptor antagonists against delayed emesis reported by some investigators [18-20]. As such, complete prevention or amelioration of delayed emesis may not be achieved with the addition of NK₁ receptor antagonists alone. Third, despite the variability of the conditioning melphalan dosages, the mean treatment dose of the entire cohort was 180 mg/m²; the mean dose of melphalan among those who developed delayed vomiting was 183 mg/m². Fourth, it is possible that addition of a number of purportedly important patient-related variables to the two pretreatment variables could further improve prophylaxis against delayed emesis. The presence of these recognized risk factors and the small number of subjects notwithstanding, our data do not suggest that female gender alone is associated with a higher risk of developing delayed symptoms among patients receiving high-dose melphalan. Moreover, the mean melphalan dose in men and women with delayed emesis was 180 mg/m² and 185 mg/m², respectively. In addition, the mean age of the (+) and (-) emesis groups were relatively similar, 62 and 56 years old, respectively. This latter finding suggests that either age alone is not independently associated with risk for delayed CIV or that the older age of the subjects in this study masked the usefulness of this factor. A history of alcohol consumption (one individual) or motion sickness (no subjects) could not be correlated with the development of delayed symptoms; neither could other co-morbid medical conditions such as diabetes.

Current recommendations for prophylaxis of the delayed emetic syndrome utilize only treatment-related factors (i.e., chemotherapy emetic-risk level).

However, these recommendations are applicable only to patients who receive standard doses of chemotherapy or other types of anticancer agents. However, if sP plays an important role in the genesis of delayed CIV, routine addition of an NK₁ receptor antagonist should be based on the likelihood of symptom development. This may apply to melphalan in the transplant setting barring significant drug-drug and drug-effect interactions. Hence, addition of aprepitant to the 5-HT₃ receptor antagonist/dexamethasone doublet may not only be rational but also beneficial in a subset of patients who receive HD-Mel [21,22].

Conclusion

These data represent an extension to (rather than validation of) our previous finding related to the association of two novel markers and risk of delayed emetic symptoms. Although it could be argued that these same markers may predict patient response to antiemetics, this conclusion is far less tenable for two reasons. First, the suggestion that substance P is not a mediator of acute emesis; and second, the addition of an NK₁ receptor antagonist would have prevented symptoms in most, if not all, of the patients who developed delayed CIV. Collectively, these data also provided the rationale for a new ongoing clinical trial to prospectively test the predictive value of these neurotransmitters in patients receiving doxorubicin-based chemotherapy.

Financial & competing interest disclosure

The clinical trial from which the data originated as well as the final data analysis was conducted using residual funds of one of the investigators (GMH). As such, no financial or material support was received specifically for completion of this research study; all of the data remain the property of the authors. No other financial relationship exists between any entity and any of the authors.

Informed consent disclosure

The authors obtained verbal and signed informed consent from every patient who participated in the clinical study.

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